

Maximizing Crop Yields

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At the time of our independence we had the capacity to produce about 50 million tonnes of food grains per year. This has now enhanced to over 130 million tonnes per year, besides increasing production of fruits, vegetables, tubers, cotton, jute, plantation crops etc. But in course of the next 20 years we have to increase our capacity to 230 million tonnes per year to feed the population of estimated over 900 million. On the other hand we find that almost every day acres of fertile land being taken away for dwelling and industrial purposes. Increasing deforestation, soil erosion and land degradation is also reducing the crop production potential of the land. The only way left is to improve soil fertility and to increase production per unit area per unit time. This has been the philosophy of the school lead by Prof. N. R. Dhar for the last half a century. He has been a leading advocate of energy conservation farming and recycling of agricultural wastes for enriching the soil and increasing production without much input of fossil fuel energy. His warning however, went unheeded till the recent energy crisis has clearly shown that food production is very vulnerable to an interruption of oil supplies and total energy inputs. The following table shows a

comparison of energy input and return in modern high yielding maize production vis-a-vis in the age old practice of hand or bullock powered maize production.

	Energy input k cal per ha.	Output/input ratio
Machine produced high yielding maize	86,66,910	216 : 1
Hand powered maize	52,762	1282 : 1

Thus, modern methods of obtaining high yields appear rather inefficient. Can we increase the efficiency of food production without the use of massive energy use? I think it is possible to maximize yield and increase the efficiency of agriculture by scientific manipulation of crop environment and efficient use of our renewable resources. If human ingenuity can place a man on the moon there should be no reason why it cannot solve the food problem.

Efficiency of crop production : The word efficiency is often used to connote performance. Thermodynamically, efficiency is the output of useful energy from a system expressed as a fraction of the

Fig. 1. Daytime hourly variations in solar radiation flux density.

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Fig. 2. Annual variations of solar radiation flux density.

energy input. In crop production, the energy stored by photosynthesis in organic compounds is an useful output from a system which has solar energy as its input.

Energy environment of crops: CO₂ from air, water, and mineral nutrients from soil are the raw materials used by plants to manufacture food with the help of solar radiation. Solar radiation is absorbed by the photosynthetic machinery of green chloroplasts and is used to reduce CO₂ to carbohydrates. The rate of photosynthesis depends on many internal and external factors. Photosynthesis includes photochemical, biochemical and thermochemical reactions which are light as well as temperature dependent. Diurnal changes in solar radiation may change the short-term photosynthesis rates. Fig. 1 shows the diurnal variations in solar radiation at Pantnagar which explains how photosynthesis rate will vary throughout the day. Fig. 2 shows monthly variation in solar radiation at Pantnagar. The distribution of solar energy shows that there are sharp changes in the energy received. During April or May more than 550 cal cm⁻² day⁻¹ are received while during cloudy winters it may be as low as 340 cal cm⁻² day⁻¹. Even in July it may be 420 cal cm⁻² day⁻¹ due to cloudy weather. The peak rate of solar radiation is received during 1200 to 1300 hrs and may reach 1.3 cal cm⁻² hr⁻¹ in June. In bright sunlight the leaves are saturated with light and the rate of photosynthesis is independent of light intensity because it becomes limited by physical and biochemical processes within the leaf.

The energy environment of plant can be described by the energy conservation equation,

Net rate of incoming energy per unit area Net rate of outgoing energy per unit area

$$(Sr + SS)S + R + LE + G + P + M = 0$$

- Sr = reflected sunlight, SS = Scattered sunlight
- S = Solar radiation flux
- R = Thermal radiation flux Ground (R_g), atmosphere (R_a) and surrounding objects
- L = Latent heat of evaporation
- E = Rate of evaporation
- G = Sensible heat flux by conduction from ground to surface
- C = Sensible heat flux by convection in air
- P = Photosynthesis

The complexity of the energy exchange with N transformation is shown in Fig. 3. Energy will flow to or from plant by radiative transfer or by conduction along a temperature gradient or by mass flow by convection. Similarly water vapour, CO₂, O₂ will flow to or from the plant along a concentration gradient and N will determine the size of the photosynthetic apparatus.

Energy transfer in plants: Plants on earth, through evolution, have adapted uniquely to the frequency distribution of solar radiation. Every plant is coupled to the radiation environment to a different degree i.e., it absorbs, reflects and transmits the incident radiation depending upon the nature of spectral radiation and the spectral characteristics of leaves, plant shape and leaf orientation. The spectral absorbance and reflectance curves for the rice plant show that they possess high

Fig. 3. Schematic diagram of energy environment and N cycling in soil-rice ecosystem.

absorbance at blue and red end of the visible wave lengths where they absorb solar radiation efficiently for maximum photosynthetic efficiency.

The complete steady state energy budget expression for a plant leaf, when there is some wind movement and when conduction term, storage term and metabolic energy are neglected is :

$$Q_{abs} = \epsilon \sigma T_s^4 + k_2 \left(\frac{V}{D} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} (T_s - T_a) +$$

$$\frac{L(T_s) S p_i(T_s) - r h S p_a(T_a)}{r_i + r_e}$$

Q_{abs} = Total amount of incident radiation absorbed by the plant surface,

ϵ = Emissivity for far infrared is 0.95 to 0.97,

σ = Stefan-Boltzman constant—
 8.13×10^{-12} cal $cm^{-2} \text{ } ^\circ K^{-4} \text{ min}^{-1}$,

T_s = Surface absolute temperatur,

k_2 = Convection constant depending upon size, shape and orientation of surface and nature of flux,

$S p_a(T_a)$ = Water vapour density of air at saturation at air temperature,

$r_i + r_e$ = Internal and external diffusion resistances,

$L(T_s)$ = Latent heat of evaporation as a function of leaf temperature (580 cal gm^{-1} at 30°),

$S p_i(T_s)$ = Water vapour density within the substomatal cavity,

$r h$ = Relative humidity,

D = Characteristic dimension (width) and

V = Wind speed.

It is seen that both environmental and plant factors interact. The environmental factors are radiation, wind speed, air temperature and relative humidity. The plant factors are absorptivity to each flux of radiation, the areas exposed to radiation and total leaf area, the leaf dimension, shape, orientation and internal diffusion resistance or stomatal geometry. For any combinations of the environmental and plant factors specific leaf temperature and transpiration rate can be obtained. This shows that environment and plant interactions are complex and consist of a temperature surface in a multidimensional space.

Fig. 4 shows diurnal soil-plant-atmosphere temperature variation in a wheat crop on 16th Jan., 1981. It is seen that there is considerable variation in soil-plant-atmosphere temperatures throughout the day. Upto 10 cm soil depth the temperature fluctuations are very large while there is little change in temperature at 30 cm soil depth. Inside the crop near ground the diurnal changes are considerable in this study and the amount of assimilate respond over the whole growing season is taken as a constant fraction of the accumulated photosynthesis.

Yield analysis : The yield of a crop is determined by the response of physiological processes to the state of the environment. We have seen that this relationship between physical environment and biological response is exceedingly complex.

The yield of a crop can be expressed as :

$$Y = C_m \times f \times t \times h$$

Y = economic yield,

C_m = Maximum rate of dry matter production achieved during the main growth period,

f = Ratio of crop growth rate expressed as mean value for the whole growing season to the maximum rate obtained mid-season,

t = Time from emergence to harvest-length of growing season, and

h = harvest index.

Many experiments with crops have demonstrated a close relationship between photosynthesis rates and solar energy income¹. This relationship depends on the spatial and angular distribution of leaves and on insolation and day length. However, the rate of dry matter production by crops especially during early growth phases is proportional to the percentage of radiation intercepted by the crop canopy.

It appears that growth rates can be calculated as the product of two factors.

a. An estimate of the maximum rate of dry matter production for a crop intercepting all the incident radiation.

b. An estimate of fraction of intercepted radiation derived from the knowledge of the leaf area index and leaf geometry.

Fig. 4. Vertical temperature profile in spas.

This method tested on a series of crops in tropics and subtropics give close agreement between measured and estimated rates of drymatter production within the limits of errors of crop sampling. Since the rate at which a crop accumulates drymatter represents a balance between the rate of production by photosynthesis and the rate of consumption by respiration, in this study the amount of assimilate respired over the whole growing season is taken as a constant fraction of the accumulated photosynthesis.

Since the analysis shows that the rate of dry matter production by any crop should be proportional to the amount of light intercepted by its foliage, any method that increases light interception should help in increasing yield. This can be achieved through several ways.

- (i) Breeding of varieties with faster rate of photosynthesis in brighter light
- (ii) Maintaining a maximum value for the efficiency of leaf photosynthesis in weak light as in rainy season and cloudy winters. Any stress, water, oxygen, nutrient deficiency or pests and diseases reduce this efficiency and hence of importance for optimum crop management practices.
- (iii) Breeding and selection of varieties with leaves which expand more quickly and senesce more slowly. Also maintaining good emergence and maintaining initial soil fertility for quick growth of leaves.
- (iv) Lengthening of growing season.
- (v) Increasing harvest index.

(vi) Increasing CO₂ concentration in air.

When leaves of crop plants are exposed to bright sunlight they assimilate CO₂ from the atmosphere at a rate nearly proportional to its concentration. Though CO₂ concentration fluctuates daily and seasonally, the annual average is about 320 volumes per million or 0.6 g/m³. If the maximum daily assimilation is about 20 g of CO₂ per m² of field area, all the CO₂ in a column of air 33 m tall would be used. It is therefore possible that during active photosynthesis during bright light as in India CO₂ may be deficient. It may be mentioned here that man's industrial activity is increasing the mean global concentration of CO₂ at about 1/10⁶ (by volume) per year.

(vii) Improving plant architecture and planting density.

Some 20 percent of the absorbed solar energy can be converted into plant material. This is a very good achievement for the photosynthetic machinery, so fragile and using a source of energy as fleeting as sunlight. But on farmers' field photosynthesis seldom converts more than 1% of the solar energy available during the growing season into economic

yield. In the recently developed high yielding varieties of wheat and rice, plant architecture has been modified so that plants do not shade each other and promote better light interception. Dwarf maize varieties with smaller tassel, high nitrate reductase activity and upper placement of ear can respond to a population density of about 150,000 plants per hectare. Even such efficient crops now photosynthesize at only about half their potential.

Major scientific break-through during 1950s in the understanding of the photosynthetic process has been followed by research designed to increase photosynthetic efficiency of plants by better understanding plant environment interactions and also application of chemicals. For example CO₂ gas in green house or dry ice in open field have substantially increased the crop yields. However, much more efficient application techniques need to be developed.

Reference

1. S. L. MONTEITH, *Phil. Trans. Roy. Soc. London*, 1977, B281, 277.